

Hooked or Empowered? The Dilemma of Mobile Phone Use among Asantekwaa SDA Junior High School (JHS) Pupils: Its Implications on Their Academic Performance

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ABSTRACT

In today's digital era, mobile phones have become indispensable tools, offering students quick access to information, communication, and educational resources. Nonetheless, the overuse of these devices for non-academic tasks has raised concerns about their influence on students' academic achievements. The study investigates the challenges associated with mobile phone usage among students at Asantekwaa SDA Junior High School (JHS) and its effects on their academic performance. The study adopted a survey design. The target population was 148 students. Therefore, no sampling technique was applied. However, 122 copies of the questionnaire were considered valid for the analysis. The study revealed that 44 (30.3%) respondents use mobile phones for 4-5 hours or more daily. According to the findings, most respondents have their mobile phones, whereas others depend on their peers and parents. Most respondents reported that mobile phone usage has negatively affected their academic performance. The study advocated for clear regulations and guidelines concerning mobile phone use in schools. The study encourages collaborative efforts among educators, parents, and policymakers to lessen the detrimental effects of excessive mobile phone use.

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INTRODUCTION

In an era characterised by rapid technological advancement, mobile phones have become essential tools that profoundly influence how people communicate, gather information, and connect with their peers and family. These devices serve as valuable tools for education, social interaction, and entertainment. However, the excessive use of these devices can pose challenges among junior high school pupils, who are in a developmental stage both academically and socially. Learners are increasingly prone to distractions stemming from the overuse of mobile devices, which can interfere with their academic focus and performance (Rideout & Robb, 2019). Pupils gain greater access to social media, video streaming services, and gaming applications. It appears that pupils often prioritise leisure activities over their educational responsibilities. This shift in focus can lead to ineffective time management and a decline in academic performance (Aljomaa et al., 2016). The uncontrollability of mobile phone use is evident in educational settings. These pupils lack adequate knowledge and proper guidance on the use of mobile devices. An earlier interaction between the researchers and the headmaster of Asantekwaa SDA Junior High School revealed a significant prevalence of mobile phone usage among pupils. The headmaster indicated that the use of these phones occurred both during class hours and after school hours. Teachers and parents have expressed their apprehensions regarding the escalating trend of smartphone overuse, recognising their potential effects on academic performance. Odgers and Jensen (2020) posited that in recent years, digital technology has increasingly consumed a greater portion of learners' time, including their lives. Parental supervision and guidance are essential in helping children use smartphones responsibly. Their roles promote learners' exposure to educational and beneficial applications of these devices (Ariston & Frahasini, 2018; Zuraidah et al., 2020).

The empirical research on the impact of excessive mobile phone use on academic performance among pupils at Asantekwaa SDA JHS in this context remains scarce. This study assesses the impact of excessive mobile phone usage on the academic achievement of pupils at Asantekwaa SDA JHS. The findings of this research will contribute to the existing body of knowledge in this area.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- RQ 1. How much time do pupils spend on mobile phones daily?
- RQ 2. How do pupils acquire mobile phones?
- RQ 3. What are the primary purposes for which pupils use mobile phones?
- RQ 4. Does excessive mobile phone use affect pupils' academic performance?

Literature review

The researchers employed the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), developed by Katz et al. (1973), as the theoretical framework guiding the study. The theory supports an investigation into whether learners use phones to satisfy cognitive, academic, emotional or social needs, which in turn has implications for their academic performance. The UGT is relevant to this study because it helps to explain the diverse motivations behind mobile phone use among Junior High School pupils (JHS) at Asantekwaa SDA. Some pupils may use their phones to access educational resources, while others may use the devices to communicate with peers or engage in self-directed learning. These forms of use imply that such learners feel empowered in their academic journey. However, excessive reliance on these devices raises concern among the general public. The study employed the theory to examine whether mobile phone use among the pupils at Asantekwaa SDA JHS serves as a tool for academic empowerment or a source of distraction that negatively impacts their academic performance.

Time students spend on mobile phone use

In recent times, the widespread accessibility and reduced costs of mobile phones have made them a vital part of daily life, particularly among the youth. These devices offer a range of benefits, including easy access to information, communication, and educational resources.

However, their use has also raised concerns about possible adverse effects. According to Unantenne (2014), 41% of students spent more than 1 hour in a single moment of sitting, 37% spent 30–60 minutes, followed by 21% who spent 1–30 minutes, and only 2% without smartphone-related activity. Related studies revealed that students in China spend more than five hours each day using their mobile phones (MyCOS Research Institute, 2018).

Samaha and Hawi (2016) found that excessive mobile phone use correlates with heightened distractions and poor academic performance. Murugan (2019) investigates the patterns of screen time among middle school students in Chennai, Tamil Nadu. Their findings revealed that out of 205 respondents, 67 (32.7%) spent an average of 3-4 hours on screen, followed by 30.7% who spent 4-5 hours. Smartphones had the highest screen time exposure (42.9%), followed by TVs (1.5%). The prolonged mobile phone use can affect personal health, including poor time management, eye strain, sleep issues, and mental health challenges, as well as anxiety and stress. Acknowledging these effects will help promote a balanced and mindful use of mobile phones among students.

Methods of Acquiring Mobile Phones

The acquisition of mobile phone access among the pupils varies widely, with some owning personal devices. Others rely on shared or borrowed phones for use in the home and school environments. The socioeconomic background of parents, parental support, and school policies may be key factors that motivate the use of mobile phones in basic schools. The acquisition of these devices can influence both the frequency of use and the purposes for which they are used, including learning, communication, or entertainment. Recently, mobile phones have emerged as vital tools for communication, education, and social interaction. They are considered luxury items; these devices are now becoming accessible to a broader segment of the population, including junior high school (JHS) pupils. The phenomenon of mobile use among young people is becoming increasingly prevalent as mobile technologies become more accessible and affordable, with device ownership among children further highlighting the trend of early smartphone use (Rideout & Robb, 2019).

The authors revealed that 35% of the respondents owned their devices, and most respondents frequently used them to access YouTube/YouTube Kids, the internet, quick search tools, and to watch streaming video services. Among the 121 children who owned a device, the average daily use was 115.3 minutes (SD = 115.1), ranging from 0.20 to 632.5 minutes. The patterns of mobile phone use and how children acquire the devices are essential for monitoring their behaviours.

The growing use of mobile phones among basic school pupils raises concerns regarding how these devices are acquired and their implications for educational and personal development. Young children are increasingly using smartphones and tablets for various activities, including entertainment, social interaction, and educational purposes (Radesky et al., 2020). These gadgets allow access to educational apps, videos, and other interactive materials that can help in the early development of thinking skills. However, if children use these devices excessively without proper guidance, they may face distractions, which could affect their behaviour and learning.

Akib et al. (2021) examined the association between excessive smartphone usage and the prevalence of dry eye symptoms among junior high school students. The results demonstrated that a significant number (98%) of the children were engaged in smartphone use, with 67% using devices owned by their guardians, 18% borrowing from other relatives, 14% possessing their personal smartphones. The increase in accessibility has contributed to a heightened familiarity among students with the various functionalities and applications that smartphones encompass (Noorhidawati et al., 2015). Understanding the pattern of mobile phone use among basic school pupils is essential for formulating effective digital learning strategies and ensuring that all learners fully benefit from mobile technologies.

Purposes for which students use mobile phones

The adoption of mobile phones among basic school pupils has increased significantly, serving multiple roles beyond fundamental communication. Studies indicated that the use of social technologies, including texting and instant messaging, within a simulated classroom setting may result in lower recall (Wood et al., 2012).

Hasanah et al. (2018) emphasised that using smartphones as educational tools enhances understanding of scientific concepts such as the respiratory system while promoting critical thinking and digital literacy skills through various functionalities. While some learners use mobile phones to support their studies, such as searching for information, using educational applications, or joining academic groups, others use them for non-academic activities that might compete with their study time. There is a need for pupils to strike a balance between productive and non-productive use of their mobile phones. Green (2019) posits that smartphone usage in classroom settings facilitates effective communication. Muflih et al. (2017) assert that in Indonesia, the popularity of smartphones is motivated by gaming and social media applications, which influence the interests and daily activities of users. The practice has led to growing concerns because of its adverse effects on students' academic performance (Muflih et al., 2017). Students engage in cooperative activities related to projects and assignments using messaging and video conferencing technologies, which enhances effective collaboration regardless of geographical barriers (Li et al., 2022). Several learners employ mobile phones to browse social media platforms, stream audio and video content, or engage in online discussions that yield little to no educational advantage. Such activities may cause distractions, lower concentration levels during instructional periods, and delays in academic activities.

Chaudhary et al. (2017) revealed that out of 653 students, 48% of the youth used their mobile phones to send text messages, 31% of respondents had received nude photographs or videos, 38% had shared sexually explicit text messages, and 20% had sent nude images or videos. The study stressed further that 71% of females and 67% of males had sent sexually suggestive messages and images to their friends. The finding indicated a connection between a preference for group interactions and a sense of belonging, which improves the ease of communication that smartphones offer. Some learners use technology to support their studies, whereas others primarily use it for leisure activities that can divert their attention.

Effects of mobile phone use among students'

In every society, the youth play a significant role in the socio-economic development of the community, serving as the foundation for progress and development. They are poised to become educators, lawmakers, judges, innovators, and leaders, influencing governance, justice, and societal values. Their knowledge, skills, and ethical principles will empower them to tackle challenges and impact policy-making for generations to come. The study by Ammunje et al. (2022) revealed that heavy smartphone use contributes to a decline in students' academic performance, with technology acting as a mediating factor. In Africa, and more specifically in Ghana, there has been a notable surge in mobile phone usage among students, often hampering their academic activities (De Bruijn et al., 2009; Porter et al., 2012; Twum, 2014). Ravizza (2014) notes that the application of these technologies in the classroom can have both beneficial and adverse effects on learning. It is worth mentioning that investing in education on the negative consequences of mobile phone use, such as its effects on moral development and overall well-being, is not merely an act of goodwill but a strategic initiative with long-term benefits.

Researchers have attributed mobile phone overuse to loneliness and weak social relationships. They also found that overuse of these devices is responsible for depression, poor sleep quality and low academic achievement (Baert et al., 2020; Han & Yi, 2019; Jniene et al., 2019; Yayan et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2023).

Torous et al. (2021) assert that the overuse of mobile phones can negatively impact health quality and social interactions within a community. The prevalence of smartphones has evolved into a lifestyle choice that may inadvertently influence social behaviours and promote unhealthy living practices (Nivette et al., 2021).

To effectively address this concern, parents may implement practical strategies that include defining specific usage parameters, maintaining regular dialogue about acceptable content, and utilising parental control tools like applications for managing screen time (e.g., Apple Screen Time and Google Family Link), content filters, and surveillance software to alleviate any negative behavioural consequences.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey approach to gather data on mobile phone use and its effects on academic performance. The method permits researchers to gather rich and reliable data directly from the population of interest. Fraenkel et al. (2019) argue that survey methods allow researchers to analyse various variables, making them well-suited to investigating the implications of this trend in the context of education.

Population

The study comprised JHS 1, JHS 2, and JHS 3 of Asantekwaa SDA Junior High School. The target population was one hundred and forty-eight (148) pupils. The intention was to elicit significant information concerning the trends and behaviours associated with mobile phone use across different classes. Including pupils from all three classes allows for a richer diversity of perspectives and experiences, which is essential for a thorough analysis of how excessive mobile phone use may impact their academic outcomes.

Sampling Method

The study employed a stratified random sampling technique to ensure that pupils from JHS 1, JHS 2, and JHS 3 were well-represented. However, considering the limited size of the overall population, the researchers ultimately included all pupils without using additional sampling techniques.

Research Location

Asantekwaa Seventh-day Adventist Junior High School is within the Kintampo North Municipal District in the Bono East Region of Ghana. It is the only junior high school in the locality, near the renowned Fuller Falls.

Data Collection

The initiation of data collection involved acquiring the necessary permissions from relevant authorities, including the head teacher. The researchers sent a formal letter to the headteacher of Asantekwaa SDA Junior High School, which articulated the purpose and objectives of the study and the type of data intended for collection. They also informed parents through the Parents– Teachers Association (PTA) during a meeting to obtain informed consent and ensure adherence to ethical guidelines. This process included administering questionnaires to gather data on the subject under study. This structured approach guaranteed that the data collection process was ethical, transparent, and aligned with the research goals.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is a methodical approach that allows researchers to organise, interpret, and draw conclusions from collected data intended to address research questions and meet the study's objectives. The analysis was conducted exclusively through a quantitative method to ensure an in-depth knowledge of the topic. The researchers used IBM SPSS Statistics Version 26 for data analysis. A total of 148 pupils received copies of the questionnaire. Out of this number, 145 completed copies were retrieved and validated for analysis, resulting in a response rate of 98%.

Ethical Considerations

The Registrar of the University approved this study. Following this approval, the participants were all informed about the purpose of the research. The researchers ensured complete confidentiality and anonymity, with no personal information disclosed during and after the data collection process. The study was strictly for academic purposes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 below presents the distribution of respondents by gender, providing insights into the gender representation in the study. The results indicated that male respondents constituted 78 (53.8%), while their female counterparts were 67 (46.2%). The results demonstrated higher male participation compared to female respondents in the study. Additionally, the results revealed that a high proportion of the respondents fell within the ages of 13–14 years, representing 46.9%, followed by 47 respondents who fell between the age brackets of 10–12 years, representing 32.4%, while 30 respondents fell within the age bracket of 15–16, indicating 20.7%.

Table 1: Background information of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Female	67	46.2
Male	78	53.8
Total	145	100
Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
10- 12	47	32.4
13- 14	68	46.9
15- 16	30	20.7
Total	145	100

Source: *Field data, 2025*

Time spent on mobile phones daily

The findings revealed that 44 respondents (30.3%) used mobile phones for 4 to 5 hours or more each day, which may indicate excessive use that could negatively impact their academic performance. Thirty-three respondents (22.8%) spent 3 to 4 hours daily on mobile devices. Additionally, 25 respondents (17.2%) indicated spending 2 to 3 hours on their phones, while only 23 individuals (15.9%) showed 0 to 1 hour per day. These results indicated a prevailing trend where most students dedicated substantial time to mobile phone activities.

Source: *Field data, 2025*

Figure 1: Time spent on mobile phones daily

Modes of Access to Mobile Phones among Students

The findings indicated that 63 respondents (43.4%) have mobile phones, followed by 52 respondents (35.9%) who reported borrowing phones from their parents. The findings demonstrated a degree of parental oversight or shared responsibility regarding phone access. On the other hand, 20 respondents (13.8%) indicated that they borrow from friends. This distribution highlighted the varying levels of access, with personal ownership emerging as the predominant means of access.

Table 2: Modes of Access to Mobile Phones among Students

Access Methods	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Own phone	63	43.4
Borrow from parents	52	35.9
Borrow from friends	20	13.8
Shared device	10	6.9
Total	145	100

Source: *Field data, 2025*

Purposes for which JHS students use mobile phones

In this section, the researchers applied the Relative Importance Index (RII) to rank factors based on their perceived importance. Thus, the factors were categorised on a five-point Likert scale, as follows: 1 = very low, 2 = low, 3 = moderate, 4 = high, and 5 = very high.

A = is the highest weight = 5

N = is the total number of respondents, which is 145

The Relative Importance Index (RII) was calculated based on the following formula:

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{A \times N}$$

$$RII = \frac{\text{Sum of weights (W1 + W2 + W3 + W4+ W5)}}{A \times N}$$

Where W is given the weight that each factor is assigned by respondents (ranking values)

$$RII: \frac{\sum w}{AN} = \frac{W1 + W2 + W3 + W4+ W5}{5 \times N}$$

$$\text{To visit social media sites} = \frac{(1 \times 11) + (2 \times 9) + (3 \times 10) + (4 \times 12) + (5 \times 10)}{5 \times 145 = 725}$$

$$: 11+18+30+48+50 = 157 / 725 = \mathbf{0.2166}$$

Table 3 below shows that the majority of the respondents use their mobile phones to access social media, which ranked 1st, followed by entertainment 2nd, watching videos ranked 3rd, communication ranked 4th, and education/learning ranked 5th. These results reflect the multifaceted use of mobile phones among students, where the specific purposes might range from productive to purely recreational.

Table 3: Purposes for which JHS students use mobile phones

Purpose	RII	Rank
To visit social media sites	0.2166	1 st
Entertainment	0.1779	2 nd
To watch videos	0.0814	3 rd
Communication	0.0745	4 th
Education/ learning	0.0276	5 th

Source: *Field data, 2025*

Effect of excessive mobile phone use among students

Out of 145 respondents, 64 (44.1%) agreed that the use of mobile phones has contributed positively to their academic performance. Only 31 (21.4%) disagreed with the statement, and 3 (2.1%) remained undecided. This data suggests that not all pupils share this sentiment. In a similar statement, 60 (41.4%) respondents strongly agreed that the use of mobile phones has improved their learning; nonetheless, only 20 (13.8%) disagreed, and 10 (6.9%) remained neutral. Of the 56 (38.6%) of the respondents agreed that using mobile phones was beneficial to their academic achievements, while 30 (20.7%) strongly disagreed, and 12 (8.3%) of the respondents maintained a neutral stance. Another finding revealed that 53 (36.55%) of the respondents agreed that mobile phones helped them stay updated, 41 (28.3%) strongly disagreed, and only 5 (3.4%) remained undecided.

Table 4: Effect of excessive mobile phone use among students

Purposes	SA	A	N	SD	D
The use of mobile phones has enhanced my academic performance.	60 (41.4 %)	40 (27.6%)	10 (6.9%)	15 (10.3%)	20 (13.8%)
Mobile phone use made my learning easier	44 (30.3%)	33 (22.8 %)	10 (6.9%)	27 (18.6%)	31 (21.4%)
My attention in class is often distracted by mobile phones	46 (31.7 %)	40 (27.6%)	5 (3.4%)	30 (20.7%)	24 (16.6%)
I have benefited from using mobile phones	56 (38.6%)	20 (13.8%)	12 (8.3%)	27 (18.6 %)	30 (20.7%)
Mobile phones provide me with timely updates.	30 (20.7%)	53 (36.55%)	5(3.4 %)	16 (11.0%)	41 (28.3%)
The use of mobile phones has positively affected my academic performance	24 (16.5%)	64 (44.1%)	3 (2.1%)	23 (15.9 %)	31 (21.4 %)
Mobile phones enhance my communication with teachers and peers	32 (22.1%)	34 (23.4%)	19 (13.1%)	27 (18.6%)	33 (22.8%)
I spend less time with my friends and family	33 (22.8%)	25 (17.2%)	18(12.4%)	43 (29.7%)	26 (17.9%)
Using my mobile phone before bed negatively impacts my sleep	34 (23.4%)	31 (21.4%)	23 (15.8 %)	33 (22.8%)	24 (16.6%)
Excessive use of mobile phones contributes to feelings of stress	30 (20.7%)	29 (20.0 %)	14 (9.7%)	37 (25.5%)	35 (24.1 %)
I spend less time engaging in physical activities	40 (27.6%)	35(24.1%)	14 (9.7%)	27 (18.6%)	29 (20.0%)
My social interactions have decreased due to mobile phone use	37 (25.5%)	20 (13.8%)	19 (13.1%)	38 (26.2%)	31 (21.4%)
Mobile phone use has caused me to develop neck or back pain	30 (20.7%)	34 (23.4%)	22 (15.2%)	33 (22.8%)	26 (17.9%)

I experience eye strain or headaches from extended mobile phone use	41 (29.0%)	22 (13.7%)	17 (8.9%)	35 (34.2%)	30 (20.7%)
I cannot manage my time due to excessive use of mobile phone	33 (22.8%)	39 (26.9%)	16 (11.0%)	32 (22.1%)	25 (17.2%)
I struggle with getting enough sleep due to excessive phone use	45 (31.0%)	36 (24.8%)	20 (13.8%)	24 (16.6%)	20 (13.8%)

Source: Field data, 2025: Note: Strongly agree = SA; Agree = A; Neutral = N; Strongly disagree = SD; Disagree = D

DISCUSSION

This study examined mobile phone use among pupils of Asantekwaa SDA Junior High School (JHS). It also highlights areas where the findings align with or diverge from previous studies.

Time spent on mobile phones daily

The analysis revealed that most respondents use their mobile phones for between four and five hours each day. This finding differs from that of Murugan (2019), who noted an average daily screen time of three to four hours. Samaha and Hawi (2016) argue that prolonged mobile phone usage is associated with distractions and a reduction in academic performance. The finding suggests that students are relatively addicted to excessive mobile phone use, which may increase the likelihood of distraction during learning activities. The difference in findings may be owing to the increasing accessibility of smartphone use among adolescents in recent years.

Methods of Access to Mobile Phones

The findings revealed that most respondents own personal mobile phones and use them for various activities. This ownership may contribute to increased engagement in non-academic pursuits. The findings are consistent with Rideout and Robb (2019), who revealed that respondents owned their mobile phone devices. The findings suggest that pupils depend on their own mobile devices to access information from various sources. These results do not support the findings of Akib et al. (2021), who reported that many respondents use their parents' smartphones. This difference could be due to variations in the social and economic backgrounds of these pupils. They may come from more financially stable families, which allows them to purchase their own mobile devices. Additionally, increasing affordability and availability of smartphones in recent years might also account for the high rate of device ownership seen in this study.

Purposes of mobile phone use among students

The results indicate that most respondents use their mobile phones to access various social media platforms. Ownership of personal electronic devices is likely to increase mobile phone usage among pupils, which may disrupt their daily routines, including both academic and recreational activities. These results do not support Li et al. (2022), who report that respondents collaborate on projects and assignments using messaging applications and videoconferencing platforms. However, they are consistent with Green (2019), who suggests that integrating smartphones into classroom settings enhances communication and promotes collaboration among students and between students and teachers. Although these platforms facilitate communication and access to information, their excessive use may contribute to distractions that negatively affect students' concentration and academic performance.

Effect of excessive mobile phone use among students

The findings indicate that the use of mobile phones improves their academic performance. This finding is consistent with Baert et al. (2020), Han and Yi (2019), and Yang et al. (2019), who report that mobile phone use among students leads to a decline in academic performance. Similarly, Ravizza (2014) and Twum (2014) note that the use of mobile phones in the classroom has positive and negative impacts on learning. Torous et al. (2021) also claim that excessive use of mobile phones contributes to adverse individual health and disrupts social interactions

within communities. Overall, high mobile phone use presents both benefits and drawbacks. It is essential to strike a balance that maximises the benefits while mitigating their adverse effects.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, the study establishes the positive and adverse effects of mobile phone use in educational contexts. These findings may guide school management, stakeholders, and policymakers in developing strategies to address excessive mobile phone use at home and in schools. The study advocated for clear regulations and guidelines governing mobile phone use in schools. The study encourages coordinated efforts among educators, parents, and policymakers to mitigate its adverse effects.

Recommendations

The study recommends that basic schools must develop comprehensive guidelines concerning mobile phone use throughout school hours. The school leadership should establish rules to manage mobile phone use within the educational environment. The responsible use of mobile phones should be a priority for school authorities, policymakers, parents, and teachers. Teachers and guardians should educate pupils on the prudent and responsible use of mobile phones. Learners should receive education on effective time management. Parents should be encouraged to oversee their children's mobile phone habits at home. There should be restrictions on phone use, particularly during study periods. The study concluded that parents should encourage children to balance their academic obligations and leisure pursuits.

Implications of the Study

The study highlighted that mobile phone use provides learners with access to educational resources and communication tools; however, excessive use presents serious academic concerns. It further suggests that mobile phone use among children is a double-edged sword, offering educational support while also contributing to distractions, reduced focus, and diminished academic performance. These findings underscore the need for a balanced approach to ensure that mobile technology enhances learning.

Limitations

The study focused on the impact of mobile phone usage on pupils' academic performance at Asantekwaa SDA Junior High School in the Bono Region. The reliance on a single school limits the generalisability of the findings. These factors may lead to some biases in the findings. Hence, there is a need for future studies to fill the gap in the literature.

Suggestion for further studies

Future studies should conduct longitudinal studies to evaluate mobile phone usage among students in higher education settings. It may also explore the challenges associated with mobile phone use across various educational institutions and geographical areas. Additionally, a mixed-methods approach would provide deeper insights by combining quantitative and qualitative data. Expanding the scope to include second-cycle schools and broader geographical locations would enhance the generalisability of findings, given that the current research is limited to a single junior high school.

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